

Molecular and Morphological documentation of *Gerres longirostris* (Lacepède, 1801); *Lutjanus monostigma* (Cuvier, 1828): from the Central Indian Ocean Islands

Nayana Narayanankutty¹

¹Biodiversity Lab, Department of Marine-Bioscience, Faculty of Ocean Science and Technology, Kerala, University of Fisheries and Ocean Studies (KUFOS), Kochi, India

²Department of Science and Technology, Kavaratti Island, UT of Lakshadweep 682555, India

Key Points:

- The first record of *Gerres longirostris* and *Lutjanus monostigma* in Lakshadweep contributes to its unique fish diversity.
- Species are confirmed through integrative taxonomy utilising COI barcoding and morphology.
- The study highlights conservation needs and calls for genetic sampling, eDNA use, and monitoring to address climate and anthropogenic threats.

Corresponding Author:

Sivanpillai Sureshkumar,
suresh@kufos.ac.in

Received: 6 September 2024

Accepted: 9 January 2025

Abstract

The present study focuses on the new distributional records of two fishes, *Gerres longirostris* and *Lutjanus monostigma*, from the Lakshadweep archipelago, India. The genera *Gerres* and *Lutjanus* are widespread in the Indo-Pacific area. These records have added these fishes to the fish diversity of the coral reefs of the only atoll formation in India. The species identification was validated using an integrative taxonomic approach. We used the mitochondrial DNA COI gene for molecular phylogenetic analysis, and our generated sequences correspond with the morphologically identified species. Our findings reveal subtle morphological and genetic variations compared to populations in other regions, suggesting potential localised adaptations. This study contributes to a better understanding of the previously undocumented populations of Lakshadweep waters.

Keywords: Taxonomy, DNA Barcoding, Mitochondrial DNA, Lakshadweep, Perciformes.

1. Introduction

The true atolls in Indian territorial waters can only be seen in the Lakshadweep archipelago, situated about 300 kilometres off the western coast of India (Spalding et al., 2001). The diverse fauna of Lakshadweep is widely dispersed throughout various ecological niches and the tropical Indo-Pacific area (Rao, 1991). At the end of the nineteenth century, expeditions for the documentation of biodiversity began (Alcock, 1901). Fish play a significant role in the econ-

omy of these islands because the nearby sea has a huge source of tuna and other reef fish. Therefore, studies on fish and fisheries were the main focus of the investigation into this area. More than 5000 fish species can be found in coral reefs (Bellwood et al., 2010). From Lakshadweep recent surveys, a total of 882 fishes were recorded (Babu et al., 2022; Babu et al., 2023; Kar et al., 2022; Kar et al., 2023; Konhamkakkada et al., 2023; Rajan et al., 2021; Sandra et al., 2022; Sreeraj et al., 2022; Sureshkumar and Idreesbabu, 2023) (Table 1).

Table 1: After Rajan et al. (2021), the number of new reports of fishes from Lakshadweep (2021-2023).

Reference	Study Area	No. of New Species Reports
Sandra et al., 2022	Kavaratti	12
Babu et al., 2022	Kavaratti	2
Kar et al., 2022	Amini	2
Sreeraj et al., 2022	Kavaratti, Kiltan, Agatti	3
Konhamkakkada et al., 2023	Kavaratti	1
Babu et al., 2023	Kavaratti	7
Sureshkumar and Idreesbabu, 2023	Kavaratti	1
Kar et al., 2023	Kavaratti	1

The most studied and prominent taxa in coral reefs are teleost fishes. The occurrence of the fish has been examined using molecular techniques to determine their relationships at the generic and species levels. Such research has provided a wealth of knowledge regarding the temporal origin of lineages in these coral reef fish communities (Cowman and Bellwood, 2011). The taxonomy sector has adopted DNA barcoding techniques as a quick and more reliable way to confirm the identity of species. According to ongoing investigations, the mitochondrial cytochrome oxidase-1 (COI) gene is a molecular marker that can reliably be used in taxonomic confirmations. This technique has long been recognised as the most flexible method for delimitation and identification since it accurately analyses high rates of sequence divergence at the species level (Ivanova et al., 2012).

The order Perciformes, has roughly 20 suborders and about 100 families, and the group exhibits a wide range of morphological characteristics. They live in both marine and freshwater environments. Members share and lack many characters, making it challenging to determine the order. Many species have a generalised body shape resembling a perch (Bray and Gomon, 2023). Molecular phylogenetics is being used to examine taxonomic, phylogenetic and evolutionary links among the biologically varied and species-rich groups of Perciformes.

Gerres longirostris (Lacepède, 1801) belongs to the family Gerreidae and is classified as Least Concern (LC). The fishes of the family Gerreidae, known as Mojarras or Silver biddies, are grouped into eight genera and comprise 100 nominal species (Eschmeyer, 2012; Fricke et al., 2022). This family is found in marine and brackish environments in tropical and subtropical climates. It can be found in intertidal areas, seagrass beds, and mangrove channels in shallow coastal waters (Castro-Aguirre, 1978; Chollet-Villalpando et al., 2014). They can be distinguished from others by their dorsal compression, protracile mouth, smooth gill bones, cycloid scales on the head, and ctenoid scales all over the body (Jacobina et al., 2020; Nelson et al., 2016). There are 28 species in the genus *Gerres* (Eschmeyer et al., 2017). *Gerres longirostris* (Lacepède, 1801) is found throughout the Indo-Pacific region (Carpenter et al., 1997) and has a maximum total length of 37 cm (Randall, 1995). Adults reside in 50 meters of crystal-clear coastal water, whereas young ones are found in lagoons and shallow waters (Iwatsuki et al., 2001). They can live alone or in groups and eat benthic invertebrates (Lieske and Myers, 1994).

Fishes of the family Lutjanidae, also known as snappers, are commercially important and are found worldwide in tropical and subtropical regions (Allen, 1985; Nelson, 1984). Additionally, they are typically demersal and live in

the shallow waters surrounding coral reefs, down to depths of 450 m. It has 185 species and 17 genera globally (Nelson, 2006). *Lutjanus* has the highest species diversity, with 69 species. The One-spot snapper, *Lutjanus monostigma* (Cuvier, 1828), is common in the Indo-Pacific region at depths of between 5 and 30 metres (Allen, 1985). They are commonly solitary and inhabit shelters providing coral reef areas like caves, large coral formations, and wreckage. Their primary diet consists of small fish and crabs.

The primary objective of this study was to document and confirm the first recorded occurrences of *Gerres longirostris* and *Lutjanus monostigma* in the Lakshadweep archipelago. This study involved detailed morphological and molecular analyses to identify the species, assess their phylogenetic relationships, and examine any potential genetic variations unique to the region. By establishing a baseline for these species in Lakshadweep, the study aims to enhance our understanding of local marine biodiversity and support future conservation efforts in the face of environmental challenges affecting the Indian Ocean.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample collection and preservation

During an exploratory survey on the molecular taxonomic approach for developing a digital catalogue of the coral reef biota of Lakshadweep to enable conservation, all specimens were collected with a gill net and scoop net operations in the lagoons of Kavaratti, Suheli, Kadamat (Figure 1). Tissue samples were collected near the upper lateral line tissue and the pectoral fin from the right side. Tissue removed from the fish was stored in 100% alcohol for molecular analysis and kept at -4°C. All specimens were fixed in formalin and preserved in 5% of formalin for further morphological identification. All the specimens were vouchered at the Department of Science and Technology, Lakshadweep. All specimens were identified systematically based on original descriptions, published literature, and keys (Allen and Erdmann, 2012; Anderson and Allen, 2001; Iwatsuki et al., 2001). Systematic characteristics were checked in WORMS, FishBase and species nomenclature and type locality following the Catalogue of Fishes (Fricke et al., 2022).

2.2. DNA extraction, amplification, and sequencing

The Invitrogen™ PureLink Genomic DNA mini kit™ was used to extract fish genomic DNA according to the manufacturer's instructions. The purity and concentration of the isolated DNA samples were analysed using Nanodrop. The mitochondrial Cytochrome Oxidase subunit 1 (COI, 730bp) gene was amplified using the previously published primers from Ward et al. (2005).

FishF1 (5'TCAACCAACCACAAAGACATTGGCAC3')

FishR1 (5'TAGACTTCTGGGTGGCCAAAGAATCA3')

PCR was performed in a 25 µl reaction volume containing 15.875 µl of nucleus-free water, 5.0 µl of 5X PCR buffer, 1.25 µl of each primer (10 pmol), 0.5 µl of dNTP (10 mM), 0.125 µl Taq polymerase (5U), and 1.0 µl (≥ 50 ng) of template DNA sample. PCR conditions were initial denaturation at 95°C for 5 min, followed by 35 cycles of 94°C at 45 sec, 58°C at 1.05 min, extension at 72°C for 1.20 min, and final extension at 72°C for 7 min. The PCR product bands were visualised in 0.8% agarose gel. The band size ranges from 700 to 800 and was sent to Agri-Genome™ for sequencing in the Sanger method.

The COI gene sequences were trimmed to a homologous region to avoid sequencing errors and were manually assembled and trimmed using BioEdit. The obtained sequence results were then identified by comparing them to the reference sequence using the BLAST (Basic Local Alignment Search Tool) program, which can be found at <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>. Available COI gene sequences of fishes under the genus *Lutjanus* and *Gerres* from their type locality or near their type locality were extracted from GenBank for phylogenetic analysis. The trimmed sequence and extracted COI sequences were aligned using the MUSCLE algorithm in MEGA X. Phylogenetic trees were constructed using corresponding nucleotides using character-based Maximum Likelihood (ML) trees. Sequences were analysed by the best-fit model, and the maximum likelihood (ML) analysis was performed in IQ-TREE 2.2.0 (Ly-Trong et al., 2022) with the best partition scheme and ultrafast bootstrap support for 1000 iterations. The pairwise genetic distance was calculated using the K2P (Kimura 2-parameter) model (Tamura et al., 2021).

Figure 1: The sampling sites of the Lakshadweep in the present study.

3. Results

Based on morphological characters and molecular taxonomy, the occurrence of *Gerres longirostris* (Lacepède, 1801) and *Lutjanus monostigma* (Cuvier, 1828), belonging to the Order Perciformes, were confirmed. Based on the earlier reports and checklist comparison, there are no records of the presence of these fish populations. From this study, we confirm that these fishes are present in the archipelago. The DNA sequences of the COI gene obtained were submitted to GenBank (*Gerres longirostris* - OP209803, OP209790, OP209791) (*Lutjanus monostigma* - OOP209810, OP209806, OP209804, OP209811)

3.1. Morphological identification

3.1.1. *Gerres longirostris* (Lacepède, 1801)

Labrus longirostris Lacepède, 1801- (Type locality- Madagascar)

Taxonomy:

Class: Actinopterygii
 Order: Acanthuriformes
 Family: Gerreidae
 Genus: *Gerres*

Synonymy:

Labrus longirostris Lacepède, 1801
Gerres acinaces Bleeker, 1854
Sparus britannus Lacepède, 1802
Xystaema darnleyense Ogilby, 1913
Gerres lineolatus Günther, 1867
Gerres longicaudus Alleyne and MacLeay, 1877
Gerres poieti Cuvier, 1829
Gerres rueppellii Klunzinger, 1884

Materials examined: Three specimens were collected from Lakshadweep during the survey period. One speci-

men (MTRLDST-126-0625) (Figure 2) was collected from the Suheli lagoon (10°02'49.2" N 72°17'06.0" E) area at a depth of about 2m on March 10, 2021, at 2.30 PM. The second specimen (MTRLDST-126-0625-A) was collected from the Kadmat intertidal (11°12'18.0" N 72°45'57.6" E) area at a depth of about 0.5m on March 13, 2022, 11.20 AM. The third specimen (MTRLDST-126-0625-B) was collected from the Kadmat inner lagoon (11°14'38.4" N 72°46'30.0" E) area at a depth of 3m on February 27, 2022.

Figure 2: *Gerres longirostris* (MTRLDST-126-0625).

Description: Silvery body with a compact and slender figure. Body with dark stripes along rows of scales above the lateral line and dusky bars below the lateral line. Dorsal fin membrane with spots at each spine and ray. Premaxillary groove scales are absent in the dorsal fin membrane with lighter black patches. The pectoral fins and anal fins are transparent. The caudal fin is deeply forked and has a darkened posterior margin. The pectoral fin length is longer than the head length, reaching up to the anus. Scales cycloid. The first dorsal spine is shorter than the second, and the first anal spine is shorter than the third anal spine—pectoral, pelvic, caudal and anal fins of a dusky yellow colour. Morphometric characters are shown in Table 2.

Distribution: South Africa, Kenya, Zanzibar, the Red Sea, Madagascar, Seychelles, Maldives, Indonesia, New Guinea, the Ryukyu Islands (Japan), Palau Islands, northern Australia, New Caledonia, and the Marquesas Islands are all included.

Remarks: *Gerres longirostris* is similar to *G. oblongus* in having similar morphological characters. Based on the morphological identification of *Gerres longirostris* characters Table 1, they show similarity with the morphological characters described by Iwatsuki et al. (2001). Morphological characters coincide with other species of *Gerres*. Only five congeners of these species, such as *G. filamentosus*, *G. limbatus*, *G. oblongus*, *G. oyena*, and *G. erythrourus*, have been recorded from the Lakshadweep archipelago.

3.1.2. *Lutjanus monostigma* (Cuvier, 1828)

Mesoprion monostigma Cuvier, 1828 (Type locality- Seychelles)

Taxonomy:

Class: Actinopterygii
 Order: Acanthuriformes
 Family: Lutjanidae
 Genus: *Lutjanus*

Synonymy:

Mesoprion monostigma Cuvier, 1828
Lutjanus lioglossus Bleeker, 1873 ·

Figure 3: *Lutjanus monostigma* (MTRLDST-124-0609).

Materials examined: Four specimens were collected. One specimen (MTRLDST-124-0609) (Figure 3) was collected from the Suheli (10°02'49.2" N 72°17'06.0" E) area at a depth of about 2 m on March 10, 2021, at 3.45 P M. The second specimen (MTRLDST-124-0609-A) was collected

Table 2: Meristics and morphometrics of *Gerres longirostris* collected from the Lakshadweep waters

Morphological Characters	MTRLDST-126-0625	MTRLDST-126-0625 - A	MTRLDST-126-0625 - B
Total length (mm)	147.02	97.14	334
Standard length (mm)	103.92	64.81	232
Measurement in % SL			
Head length	32.05	37.84	32.02
Body depth	38.25	39.62	35.34
Pre dorsal length	37.37	47.58	42.30
Preanal length	67.96	75.83	70.81
Pre pelvic length	37.57	43.17	35.18
Pre pectoral length	32.92	38.58	29.16
Dorsal fin base	54.82	54.23	54.46
Anal fin base	19.00	19.39	17.26
Anal fin length	12.33	12.62	12.99
Dorsal fin length	20.40	18.96	22.77
Caudal fin length	39.56	40.68	36.96
Caudal peduncle width	11.90	13.00	11.70
Measurement in % HL			
Snout length	31.52	34.13	32.69
Eye diameter	26.98	25.84	21.61
Maxilla length	39.02	22.95	38.26
Meristic Characters			
Dorsal fin rays	IX+10	IX+10	IX+10
Anal fin rays	III+7	III+7	III+7
Pelvic fin rays	I+6	I+6	I+6
Pectoral fin rays	17	17	17
Lateral line scales	44	44	44
Scales above/below lateral line	$7^{1/2} / 12^{1/2}$	$7^{1/2} / 12^{1/2}$	$7^{1/2} / 12^{1/2}$

Table 3: Meristics and morphometrics of *Lutjanus monostigma* collected from the Lakshadweep waters

Morphological Characters	MTRLDST-124-0609	MTRLDST-124-0609 - A
Total length (mm)	714.95	103.94
Standard length (mm)	419.62	72.02
Measurement in % SL		
Head length	15.67	46.2
Body depth	9.29	26
Pre dorsal length	15.17	49.16
Preanal length	26.19	78.7
Pre pelvic length	15.39	48.34
Pre pectoral length	14.47	44.39
Dorsal fin base	19.07	56.31
Anal fin base	5.23	17.62
Anal fin length	6.03	20.43
Dorsal fin length	5.35	21.17
Caudal fin length	10.49	32.15
Caudal peduncle width	5.03	14.91
Measurement in % HL		
Snout length	35.52	34.16
Eye diameter	21.5	16.73
Maxilla length	42.45	40.56
Meristic Characters		
Dorsal fin	X+14	X+14
Anal fin	III+8	III+8
Pelvic fin	I+5	I+5
Pectoral fin	16	16
Lateral line scales	63	54

from the Kadmat intertidal (11°12'18.0" N 72°45'57.6" E) area at a depth of about 0.5m on March 13, 2022 at 11.00 AM. On February 8, 2022, at 8.20 AM, the third (MTRLDST-124-0609 - B) and fourth (MTRLDST-124-0609 - C) specimens were collected from the Kavaratti intertidal area (10°33'39.6" N 72°38'49.2" E).

Description: Fins are yellow-coloured. Emarginate caudal

fin. The body is generally whitish to pinkish, with grey at the back and pink near the mouth. A black spot below the dorsal fin intersects the lateral line. For juveniles, the spot is round. The dorsal fin is not very indented. The body is slightly slimmer. Mouth oblique. The dorsal profile of the head is gently sloped. The maxilla extends below the front border of the eye. Morphometric characters are shown in

Table 3.

Distribution: East Africa, the Persian Gulf, Socotra, Seychelles, Madagascar, and the Mascarenes extend east to Kiribati (Line Islands) and Pitcairn and north to southern Japan, Australia, New Caledonia, and Rapa.

Remarks: *Lutjanus monostigma* is closely related to *L. russelli*, *L. fulviflamma*, *L. ehrenbergii*, *L. johnii*, and *L. rivulatus*. They have similar black spots on the lateral line based on morphological characters. From Lakshadweep, a total of seventeen species are reported.

3.2. Molecular analysis

The maximum likelihood tree of *Gerres longirostris* (Figure 4) samples were clustered together with retrieved sequences of *G. longirostris* from GenBank (Accession no: KP194171, JF493521, KU317885, KU499806, KU499805) with bootstrap values of 93%. The phylogenetic analysis shows monophyly and fewer genetic distances between them. Due to their evolutionary similarity, *G. longirostris* and *G. oblongus* are in one cluster. The intraspecific nucleotide distances for *Gerres longirostris* were low, ranging from 0% to 0.7%. The interspecific differences between other *Gerres* species ranged to 24%. The COI sequence analysis revealed the average nucleotide frequencies as 28.8%(T), 29.6%(C), 23.2%(A) and 18.4%(G).

Phylogenetic analysis of *Lutjanus monostigma* was inferred using the maximum likelihood method (Figure 5). All the generated sequences of *L. monostigma* from Lakshadweep formed a single clade with 100% bootstrap value with their identical sequences from GenBank (KC130845, MK566974, HQ564448, KU943922). The genetic distance between these intraspecific nucleotide sequences ranged between 0 to 0.9%. The interspecific differences between other *Lutjanus* species are 17%. The largest difference was found between *L. gibbus* and *L. agennes* (17%). Average nucleotide frequency analysis shows the range of 28.2%(T), 28.5%(C), 24.8% (A), and 18.5%(G).

4. Discussion

The current study presents the first molecular and morphological documentation of *Gerres longirostris* and *Lutjanus monostigma* from the Lakshadweep archipelago. These findings enhance biodiversity knowledge in the region and underscore the need for continued species surveys.

Gerres longirostris and *Lutjanus monostigma* were distributed widely in the Indo-Pacific region (Allen, 1985; Iwatsuki et al., 2001). Along the Indian coast, it was reported from all the coastal waters. This common species has not been reported in Lakshadweep, possibly due to misidentification with other species of the same genus or insufficient sampling efforts. In another way, the new species are introduced into a new area naturally and anthropogenically. Climate change is an indicator of biological species shift. When it causes habitat loss, habitat disturbance shifts in geographic ranges, Phenology, recruitment, and growth (Brander, 2010; Hollowed et al., 2013; Stock et al., 2011). The species in the Lakshadweep Islands may have arrived as a result of a biogeographic shift, potentially being transported to the islands during their larval stages (Randall et al., 2019). Pollution, shoreline development, and fishing are generally man-made disturbances (Hollowed et al., 2013).

Twenty-two morphological characters that can be used in their identification were selected for the present study. For the molecular evaluation, we analysed ten specimens to generate sequences of the COI gene. BLAST results showed 95–100% similarity with pre-existing sequences in the GenBank. This study demonstrated evidence to support monophyly for the species. The findings of this study contribute to a better understanding of the taxonomy, phylogenetic and genetic diversity of *Gerres longirostris* and *Lutjanus monostigma*. The comparison of sequences for the analysis was selected from their type locality. The intraspecific difference between *G. longirostris* (0-0.7%) and *L. monostigma* (0-0.9%) species was relatively low. This minor genetic variation may be reflective of localised adaptations to unique environmental conditions in the Lakshadweep archipelago, such as variation in salinity, reef structure, or prey availability, which influence genetic differentiation over time.

Taxonomy and systematics are still confused with this species because of the low level of morphometric variability (Karanovic et al., 2016). It is concluded that DNA barcoding is an effective and modern molecular technique for the documentation of identification based on morphological characters. Our study is based on the first occurrence of two fish species: *Gerres longirostris* (Lacepède, 1801) and *Lutjanus monostigma* (Cuvier, 1828) from Lakshadweep waters. Our study contributes to documenting

Tree scale: 0.1

Figure 4: Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of members of the Genus *Gerres* based on mitochondrial COI gene sequences, with *Terapon jarbua* as an out-group. Values along the nodes are percentage bootstraps based on 1000 iterations.

the local fish diversity. Lakshadweep is a diverse and rich ecosystem. We confirmed this species using the analysis of morphological taxonomy and molecular barcoding. COI gene barcoding is a standardised and alternative method of traditional morphometric analysis (Hebert et al., 2003).

Further research is needed to deepen our understanding of the population structure and genetic connectivity of the species in the Lakshadweep archipelago and beyond. Expanding genetic sampling and using environmental DNA (eDNA) techniques could enhance understanding of gene flow and population structure across the Indian Ocean (Thomsen and Willerslev, 2015). Additionally, long-term morphological monitoring in response to environmental fluctuations would clarify how phenotypic plasticity contributes to adaptive responses in these species (Fox et al., 2019). Both species are currently listed as “Least Concern” on the IUCN Red List, indicating that they are not considered to be at immediate risk of extinction on a global scale. However, this status does not preclude potential local threats to their populations, particularly in sensitive ecosystems like the Lakshadweep archipelago, where pressures

from habitat degradation, overfishing, and climate change continue to increase. Conservation efforts that focus on safeguarding habitat quality and implementing sustainable fishing practices will be essential to mitigate local pressures and help ensure the resilience of *G. longirostris*, *L. monostigma*, and other marine species within the Indian Ocean.

5. Conclusion

Our study is a comprehensive molecular and morphological analysis of *Gerres longirostris* and *Lutjanus monostigma* populations from the Lakshadweep archipelago, contributing valuable data to the knowledge of fish diversity in the Central Indian Ocean Islands. This study provides the first known record of *Gerres longirostris* and *Lutjanus monostigma* from the Lakshadweep archipelago, underscoring the archipelago’s role as a habitat for diverse fish species previously unreported in this region. We confirm the taxonomic classification of both species through morphological descriptions and genetic profiling, highlighting minor intraspecific variations likely influenced by environmental

Tree scale: 0.1

Figure 5: Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of members of the Genus *Lutjanus* based on mitochondrial COI gene sequences, with *Aphareus furca* as an out-group. Values along the nodes are percentage bootstraps based on 1000 iterations.

adaptation of the location. The genetic divergence suggests that these adaptations improve resilience to ecological pressures.

The genetic and morphological data are crucial for conservation and provide a baseline for future monitoring of organism population and diversity. These species are vital for the stability of reef and coastal ecosystems, making it essential to protect them from natural and anthropogenic threats. Conducting more genetic sampling from different locations, along with the use of new techniques like environmental DNA (eDNA), can enhance our understanding of population structure and gene flow among neighbouring

regions. Also, incorporating the long-term monitoring of morphological traits in response to environmental changes will improve our understanding of adaptive changes within these species. Our study establishes a foundation for future research and underscores the importance of documenting regional biodiversity for effective conservation efforts in the Indian Ocean.

Funding sources

The Department of Science and Technology (DST-SERB), Government of India, provides financial support to Sivanpillai Sureshkumar under the Core Research Grant (CRG/2020/004498).

Author Contributions

Conceptualisation: NN, MT and SS.
Investigation and field surveys: NN and MT.
Laboratory analysis: NN, MT and PCM.
Data analyses: NN, MT and SS.
Writing—original draft preparation: NN and SS.
Edited and Revised: SS

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interest/ personal relationships, which may be considered as potential competing interests. Dr S Sureshkumar reports that financial support was provided by the DST-SERB core project.

Data Availability Statement

All data generated in this study are included in this published article and GenBank (NCBI) <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank>, where novel sequences with accession numbers OP209803, OP209790, OP209791, OOP209810, OP209806, OP209804, OP209811 were deposited.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to sincerely thank the DST-SERB core project (CRG/2020/004498) for the financial support for the work. We thank the DST staff for their help in collecting the specimens used in the study.

Ethics approval

All required permits for collection and ethical approval were acquired from the Department of Science and Technology (DST), Union Territory of Lakshadweep, Kavaratti, Lakshadweep (LD–0400/1/2/2017–S&TUTLKS), and follow the general guidelines from the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA), Government of India.

References

Alcock, A. (1901). *Illustrations of the zoology of the royal indian marine surveying steamer investigator: crustacea* (Vol. 9).
Allen, G., & Erdmann, M. (2012). *Reef fishes of the east indies* [Vol. 1: 1-424, Vol. 2: 425-856, Vol. 3: 857-1292]. Tropical Reef Research.
Allen, G. (1985). *Snappers of the world. an annotated and illustrated catalogue of lutjanid species known to date* (Vol. 125).

Anderson, W. J., & Allen, G. (2001). Lutjanidae. jobfishes. In K. Carpenter & V. Niem (Eds.), *Fao species identification guide for fishery purposes. the living marine resources of the western central pacific* (pp. 2840–2918, Vol. 5). FAO.
Babu, K., Ho, H., Mariyambi, P., & Sureshkumar, S. (2022). Two new species of the codling fish genus *Physiculus* from Lakshadweep, India (Gadiformes: Moridae). *Zootaxa*, 5104(1), 111–124. DOI: 10.11646/zootaxa.5104.1.6.
Babu, S., Anto, A., Sreeram, M., & Sreenath, K. (2023). Seven new distributional records of cryptobenthic reef fishes in lakshadweep, india. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 103, e37. DOI: 10.1017/S0025315423000279.
Bellwood, D., Klanten, S., Cowman, P., Pratchett, M., Konow, N., & Van Herwerden, L. (2010). Evolutionary history of the butterflyfishes (f: Chaetodontidae) and the rise of coral feeding fishes. *Journal of Evolutionary Biology*, 23(2), 335–349. DOI: 10.1111/j.1420-9101.2009.01904.x.
Brander, K. (2010). Impacts of climate change on fisheries. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 79(3-4), 389–402.
Bray, D., & Gomon, M. (2023). Perches and allies, PERCI-FORMES in Fishes of Australia [Accessed June 08, 2023].
Carpenter, K., Krupp, F., Jones, D., & Zajonz, U. (1997). *Living marine resources of kuwait, eastern saudi arabia, bahrain, qatar, and the united arab emirates* [FAO species identification field guide for fishery purposes]. FAO.
Castro-Aguirre, J. (1978). *Catálogo sistemático de los peces marinos que penetran a las aguas continentales de méxico con aspectos zoogeográficos y ecológicos*.
Chollet-Villalpando, J., De La Cruz-Agüero, J., & Garcia-Rodriguez, F. (2014). Comparison of urohyal bone morphology among gerreid fish (Perciformes: Gerreidae). *Italian Journal of Zoology*, 81(2), 246–255. DOI: 10.1080/11250003.2014.912681.
Cowman, P., & Bellwood, D. (2011). Coral reefs as drivers of cladogenesis: Expanding coral reefs, cryptic extinction events, and the development of biodiversity hotspots. *Journal of Evolutionary Biology*, 24(12), 2543–2562. DOI: 10.1111/j.1420-9101.2011.02391.x.
Eschmeyer, W. N. (2012). Catalogue of Fishes. Updated Internet Version of 02 October 2012. Catalog Databases of CAS Cited in FishBase (Website).
Eschmeyer, W. N., Fricke, R., & Van der Laan, R. (2017). *Catalogue of fishes: Genera, species, references*.
Fox, R., Donelson, J., Schunter, C., Ravasi, T., & Gaitán-Espitia, J. (2019). Beyond buying time: The role of plasticity in phenotypic adaptation to rapid environmental change. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B*, 374(1768), 20180174.

- Fricke, R., Eschmeyer, W., & Van der Laan, R. (2022). Eschmeyer's catalog of fishes: Genera, species, references.
- Hebert, P. D., Cywinska, A., Ball, S. L., & DeWaard, J. R. (2003). Biological Identifications Through DNA Barcodes. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences*, 270(1512), 313–321. DOI: 10.1098/rspb.2002.2218.
- Hollowed, A., Barange, M., Beamish, R., Brander, K., Cochrane, K., Drinkwater, K., Foreman, M., Hare, J., Holt, J., Ito, S., & Kim, S. (2013). Projected impacts of climate change on marine fish and fisheries. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 70(5), 1023–1037. DOI: 10.1093/icesjms/fst081.
- Ivanova, N. V., Clare, E. L., & Borisenko, A. V. (2012). Dna barcoding in mammals. In W. Kress & D. Erickson (Eds.), *DNA Barcodes* (pp. 153–182, Vol. 858). Humana Press, Totowa, NJ. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-61779-591-6_8.
- Iwatsuki, Y., Kimura, S., & Yoshino, T. (2001). Redescription of *Gerres longirostris* (Lacepède, 1801) and *Gerres oblongus* Cuvier in Cuvier and Valenciennes, 1830, included in the *Gerres longirostris* complex (Perciformes: Gerreidae). *Copeia*, 2001(4), 954–965. DOI: 10.1643/0045-8511(2001)001[0954:ROGLLD]2.0.CO;2.
- Jacobina, U., Torres, R., De Mello Affonso, P., Dos Santos, E., Calado, L., & De Araújo Bitencourt, J. (2020). DNA barcoding reveals cryptic diversity and peculiar phylogeographic patterns in mojarras (Perciformes: Gerreidae) from the Caribbean and South-western Atlantic. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 100(2), 277–283. DOI: 10.1017/S0025315419001206.
- Kar, C., Shabeena, K., Mohammednowshad, B., Idreesbabu, K., Mol, V., & Sureshkumar, S. (2022). A distributional record of the lattice soldierfishes, *Myripristis violacea* Bleeker, 1851 and *Myripristis hexagona* Lacepede, 1802 (Actinopterygii: holocentriformes: Holocentridae) from Lakshadweep Archipelago, West Coast of India. *Thalassas: An International Journal of Marine Sciences*, 38(2), 1253–1259. DOI: 10.1007/s41208-022-00456-y.
- Kar, C., PC, M., KS, S., & KK, I. (2023). On the Occurrence and DNA Barcoding of Darwin's Slimehead, *Gephyroberyx darwini* (Johnson, 1866) in the Laccadive Archipelago, Western Indian Ocean. *Thalassas: An International Journal of Marine Sciences*, 1–7. DOI: 10.1007/s41208-023-00572-3.
- Karanovic, T., Djurakic, M., & Eberhard, S. (2016). Cryptic species or inadequate taxonomy? implementation of 2d geometric morphometrics based on integumental organs as landmarks for delimitation and description of copepod taxa. *Systematic Biology*, 65(2), 304–327. DOI: 10.1093/sysbio/syv088.
- Konhamkakkada, I., Kinattumkara, B., Raghavan, R., & Sivanpillai, S. (2023). A new species of spiny eel of the genus *Notacanthus* Bloch 1788 (Notacanthiformes: Notacanthidae) from the Indian Ocean. *Journal of Fish Biology*. DOI: 10.1111/jfb.15408.
- Lieske, E., & Myers, R. (1994). *Coral reef fishes, indo-pacific and caribbean including the red sea*. Harper Collins Publishers.
- Ly-Trong, N., Naser-Khdour, S., Lanfear, R., & Minh, B. Q. (2022). Alisim: A fast and versatile phylogenetic sequence simulator for the genomic era. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 39(5), msac092. DOI: 10.1093/molbev/msac092.
- Nelson, T. (1984). A comparison of current measures of the accuracy of feeling-of-knowing predictions. *Psychological Bulletin*, 95(1), 109.
- Nelson, J. (2006). *Fishes of the world (4th ed.)* John Wiley & Sons.
- Nelson, J., Grande, T., & Wilson, M. (2016). *Fishes of the world*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Rajan, R., Rajan, P., Mishra, S., CN, A., & AT, D. (2021). Fishes of lakshadweep archipelago: New records, review and a revised checklist. *Marine Biodiversity Records*, 14(1), 1–13. DOI: 10.1186/s41200-021-00208-6.
- Randall, J. (1995). *Coastal fishes of oman*. University of Hawaii Press.
- Randall, J., Busby, M., Spear, A., & Mier, K. (2019). Spatial and temporal variation of late summer ichthyoplankton assemblage structure in the eastern chukchi sea: 2010–2015. *Polar Biology*, 42, 1811–1824. DOI: 10.1007/s00300-019-02555-8.
- Rao, G. (1991). Lakshadweep: General features. *Fauna of Lakshadweep, State Fauna Series*, 2, 5–40.
- Sandra, B., Anto, A., Sreeram, M., Sreenath, K., Aju, K., Sreekumar, K., Akhilesh, K., & Joshi, K. (2022). New distributional records of twelve reef fishes from lakshadweep waters, india. *Thalassas: An International Journal of Marine Sciences*, 1–13. DOI: 10.1007/s41208-022-00424-6.
- Spalding, M., Ravilious, C., & Green, E. (2001). *World atlas of coral reefs*. University of California Press.
- Sreeraj, C., Sen, A., & Raghunathan, C. (2022). Report of three crypto-benthic reef fishes from lakshadweep islands, india. *Journal of Asia-Pacific Biodiversity*, 15(4), 647–652. DOI: 10.1016/j.japb.2022.08.004.
- Stock, C. A., Alexander, M. A., Bond, N. A., Brander, K. M., Cheung, W. W., Curchitser, E. N., Delworth, T. L., Dunne, J. P., Griffies, S. M., Haltuch, M. A., Hare, J. A., Hollowed, A. B., Lehodey, P., Levin, S. A., Link, J. S., Rose, K. A., Rykaczewski, R. R., Sarmiento, J. L., Stouffer, R. J., ... Werner, F. E. (2011). On the use of IPCC-class models to assess the impact of climate on Living Marine Resources. *Progress in Oceanography*, 88(1), 1–27. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2010.09.001.

- Sureshkumar, S., & Idreesbabu, K. K. (2023). Checklist of Sand Perches (Pinguipedidae) in Indian Waters with a New Record of *Parapercis millepunctata* (Günther 1860) from Lakshadweep, India. *Thalassas: An International Journal of Marine Sciences*, 39(2), 577–585. DOI: [10.1007/s41208-023-00562-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s41208-023-00562-5).
- Tamura, K., Stecher, G., & Kumar, S. (2021). MEGA11: Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis Version 11. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 38, 3022–3027. DOI: [10.1093/molbev/msab120](https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msab120).
- Thomsen, P., & Willerslev, E. (2015). Environmental dna—an emerging tool in conservation for monitoring past and present biodiversity. *Biological Conservation*, 183, 4–18.
- Ward, R., Zemlak, T., Innes, B., Last, P., & Hebert, P. (2005). Dna barcoding australia’s fish species. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 360(1462), 1847–1857. DOI: [10.1098/rstb.2005.1716](https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2005.1716).